

Multipurpose Rover Robot

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ABSTRACT

This project comes with the idea of building a rover robot with rocker bogie mechanism. It is favored for design for wheeled robots mainly because it has robust capabilities to deal with obstacles. This mechanism helps a robot to move easily in uneven surface. This robot can also climb stairs adjusting itself according to the height of the step and even help in fire detection in the case of fire. This robot can also change its direction by the two wheeled differential drivesystem. This robot can detect abnormal and dangerous situation with the help of thermal body detection and send notification through internet or send a message to cellular phone. This robot also contains a surveillance camera which will help in increased sense of security and help in surveillance from a distant place. This rover robot can also be used in army bases as it has rover mechanism which helps in movement of the robot in uneven surfaces and even serves the purpose of surveillance.

Keywords –Rover Robot, Surveillance

I. INTRODUCTION

Surveillance is that the technique for perceptive a location, a part or someone for defense and security purpose. This activity continuously happens in an exceedingly military, police, publicplaces and even in homes these daysfor watching and to regulate the dirty activities. We choosea rocker-bogie mechanism for our mechanism as a result of its extremely stable suspension thatis capable of operative in multi tract surfaces whereas keeping all wheels to bear with ground.This mechanism is that the suspension arrangement employed in multipurpose rover robots introduced for surveillance purpose, obstacle detection and easy movement even in difficult place to move. The development of advanced robotic systems has revolutionized various industries, including surveillance and exploration. One such remarkable innovation is the Rover Robot, designed specifically for climbing uneven surfaces and conducting surveillance tasks in challenging environments. This state-of-the-art robot combines cutting-edge technology and intelligent design to overcome obstacles and gather valuable information in both indoor and outdoor settings.

Climbing Uneven Surfaces:

The Rover Robot is engineered with exceptional climbing capabilities, allowing it to navigate and conquer a wide range of uneven terrains. Its robust and adaptable chassis, equipped with specialized wheels, tracks, or limbs, ensures stability and traction on various surfaces such as rocky terrains, stairs, and inclines. By utilizing sophisticated sensors and algorithms, the Rover Robot can analyze the terrain in real-time and adjust its movements accordingly, making

it highly proficient in overcoming obstacles and traversing challenging landscapes.

Surveillance Capabilities:

Beyond its climbing prowess, the Rover Robot boasts advanced surveillance capabilities, making it an invaluable tool for security and monitoring purposes. Integrated high-resolution cameras, including both visible light and thermal imaging, enable the robot to capture clear and detailed images and videos in any lighting condition. This allows for enhanced situational awareness, even in low-light environments or areas with limited visibility.

Remote Operation and Communication:

The Rover Robot can be remotely operated by a human operator or programmed to follow pre-defined routes and perform specific tasks autonomously. A user-friendly control interface allows operators to monitor the robot's movements, access camera feeds, and control its functions remotely. Real-time communication capabilities, such as audio and video streaming, facilitate seamless interaction between the robot and the operator, enabling effective coordination and decision-making.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Thajid Ibna Rouf Uday, Nazib Ahmad, Amit Ghosh, Junaid Jahin, Md. Mushfiqur Rahman[1] In this paper, we investigate a fully operational mobile platform rover “Mars Rover UIU” which can perform as human assistant in analyzing the surface of planet Mars and complete the assigned scientific analysis and Testing. The rover is designed with modified rocker-bogie, SMPS technology-based power system, a robotic Arm with 5 degrees of freedom and is controlled using Microsoft Xbox 360 controller. “Mars Rover UIU” can perform various tasks such as Scientific Analysis, Extreme Retrieval and Delivery, Equipment Servicing and Autonomous traversal of a variety of terrains (sandy, rocky, vertical drops, steep slopes). It can examine existence of microbial life by studying geological context such as evidence of water flow, present minerals and soil structure. It can assist astronauts by retrieving and delivering objects to destinations marked by GPS coordinates. Tejas Bamne, Siddhi Jadhav, Shrutika Borkar, Shailesh[2] The rocker-bogie suspension mechanism it's currently NASA's favored design for wheeled robots, mainly because it has robust capabilities to deal with obstacles. Rocker-bogie mechanism was used in the Mars rover. This mechanism helps a robot to displace from one place to another very easily even after having an uneven surface. Usually the four-wheeled robot having a normal steering mechanism cannot always move over the very uneven surface. So, this mechanism helps a robot to climb any kind of surface Jaya Balaji, Vimal Khanna, Avinashi Nigam, Mohamed Zeeshan M and Harish[3] Since the invention of the wheel, Man has sought to reduce effort to get things done easily. Ultimately, it has resulted in the invention of the Robot, an Engineering Marvel. Up until now, the biggest factor that hampers wide proliferation of robots is locomotion and maneuverability. They are not dynamic enough to conform even to the most commonplace terrain such as stairs. To overcome this, we are proposing a stair climbing robot that looks a lot like the human leg and can adjust itself according to the height of the step. But, we are currently developing a unit to carry payload of about 4 Kg. The automatic adjustment in the robot according to the height of the stair is done by connecting an Android device that has an application programmed in OpenCV with an Arduino in Host mode. The Android

Device uses its camera to calculate the height of the stair and sends it to the Arduino for further calculation. This design employs an Arduino Mega ADK 2560 board to control the robot and other home fabricated custom PCB to interface it with the Arduino Board. Guabgming Song, Kaijian Yin, Yaoxi Zhou, Xiuzhen Cheng [4] Most traditional home robots have always had problems with stairs, doorsills and other obstacles that humans cross with ease in cluttered indoor environments. This paper presents the development and characterization of a surveillance robot with hopping capabilities for home security. The proposed robot, which is 9 cm in height and 250 g in weight, can leap over obstacles more than 4 times its own size. It depends on the elastic elements in a six-bar linkage leg system to enable hopping locomotion. It can also roll freely on flat floors and change its directions by the two-wheeled differential drive system. It adopts the ZigBee protocol for wireless communication and therefore can be added to a ZigBee-based home control network as a mobile video sensor node. Koki Kikuchi, Keisu Sakaguchi, Takayuki Sudo, Naoki Bushida, Yasuhiro [5] In this study, we propose a simple hopping mechanism using the vibration of a two-degree-of-freedom system for a wheel-based stair-climbing robot. The robot, consisting of two bodies connected by springs and a wire, hops by releasing energy stored in the springs and quickly travels using wheels mounted in its lower body. The trajectories of the bodies during hopping change in accordance with the design parameters, such as the reduced mass of the two bodies, the mass ratio between the upper and lower bodies, the spring constant, the control parameters such as the initial contraction of the spring and the wire tension. This property allows the robot to quickly and economically climb up and down stairs, leap over obstacles, and land softly without complex control. In this paper, the characteristics of hopping motion for the design and control parameters are clarified by both numerical simulations and experiments. Ren C. Luo, Te Y. Hsu, Tung Y. Lin, Kuo SU [6] The security system of home and building is an important issue to human daily life. We develop a multiple remote interface security system (MRISS), that integrated with intelligent security robot (ISR), security supervise computer, GSM module, RF interface and appliances control module. The multiple remote interface security system can detect abnormal and dangerous situation and notify us through Internet, or send the message to cellularphone through GSM module. The MRISS can control the appliance control module using wireless RF interface. The user can remote control appliance using cell phone through GSM module, too. The appliance module can feedback reaction result to the user through cell phone. First, we develop the communication protocol in MRISS, and design the multiple interface security robot, security module and appliance control module. Then we implement the MRISS function using the proposed method applying in security detection and appliance control. Sen Gupta Shubham sen Gupta [7] In present day scenario of military and defense system of India, there is a lack of some technologies. We know that the bomb detection is basically carried out by using a human bomb squad or dogs which carries the involvement of living beings and their loss can be very costly in order to just stop this mishap we have designed a robot that could actually defuse the bomb from a distance wirelessly as this robot will have a mechanical arm for itself which will be used for bomb diffusion using hand gesture control and will have a clipper to clip the wires as well as it is loaded with a Wi-Fi camera which is self-capable of capturing, live streaming and recording, at day as well as at night and can capture at 360 degrees in horizontal plane and 120 degrees on vertical plane which will be used for surveillance and identification purposes. R.A Lindeman, C.J. Voorhers [8] These rovers, named Spirit and Opportunity, were each sent on their own scientific mission of exploration. Their objective was to

work as robotic geologists. After more than a year the vehicles are still in excellent health, and returning vast amounts of scientific information on the ancient water processes that helped form Mars. Key to the success of the rovers was the development of their advanced mobility system. In this paper the mobility assembly, the mechanical hardware that determines the vehicles mobility capability, is described. The details of the design, test, and performance of the mobility assembly are shown to exceed the mission requirements

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this implementation we are implementing Rover Robot which can climb uneven surface and to detect object using ultra sonic sensor and use to detect fire using fire sensor DC motor is fixed and DC motor is controlled DC motor driver for movement of robot and rover robot is used for surveillance where wifi is connected to ESP8266 wifi module.

Fig.3.1 Block diagram of rover robot

Rocker bogie mechanism is a mechanism mainly employed within the mars rovers to conquer the basic terrains while keeping balance. It's NASA's preferred mechanism for room automobiles and rovers. It contains 2 arms with steering wheel mounted to each and every. Each arm is attached by way of a movable joint. This allows to employ a suspension-based mechanism which distributes the automobile ton as consistently as you possibly can actually on protrusions as well as unusual surfaces. The look involves a springtime totally free suspension dependent differential

drive process which enables the bogie to go more than rubble, pebbles easily. The cameras and sensors installed on a rover should be healthy to function also and properly to increase the life span of theirs. Additional vibrations as well as jerks result in quicker damage within receptors, circuit boards as well as digital cameras. The rocker bogie mechanism was created trying to keep this particular of brain by offering optimum stableness in all of the terrains. As a result, we examine the layout and also fabrication on the rocker bogie mechanism by fabrication of this particular basic surfaces automobile making use of ideas of the bogie mechanism. All-terrain movable robots are totally different from some other standard movable robots, since they think about the impact of unstructured surface and the environment of its. Thus, the robots are created to work efficiently on all-natural terrains which could be sloped, difficult, as well as deformable and therefore are utilized within these kinds of areas as serious room exploration brilliance as well as recovery as well as army. The rocker bogie suspension product is a passive spring less as well as symmetric mechanism. Each and every edge on the rocker bogie carries a bogie and a rocker: the rocker is attached to the back-steering wheel, and also the center steering wheel as well as the forward steering wheel are linked with the bogie. The 2 sides of the paper of rocker bogie are linked through the differential bar linked to the primary body, and this guarantees the 6 wheels will be in exposure to the soil constantly giving a steady wedge just for the systematic tools & receptors. The rocker arm as well as bogie are built by using various PVC and PVC pipes perspective pipe as well as for interconnecting all of the arms, we're consuming SHM strip with appropriate fastened. For linking the steering wheel, we're planning to utilize cross match jigs to repair rigidly as well as within of the steering wheel DC motor' are repaired as well as since it is equipped within the steering wheel it is able to bring down the winter perturbation also additionally, it brings down the vibration within the body. Digital camera, ultra-sonic sensor, Barometric sensor, Temperature sensor are managed by ESP8266 is in touch with 12v battery power. Plus, most 6 engines are linked through the exact same 12v electric battery, along with overall rover are managed through telephone or maybe pleasure stick that is attached through WIFI component. The rocker bogie style comprising of absolutely no springs as well as stub axles within every steering wheel that enables the chassis to get more than virtually any hurdles, like rubble, ditches, sand, and so on. Which are further up to increase the wheel's diameter of dimension while trying to keep many wheels along the floor optimum period.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Rocker Bogie Mechanism can move on a curved path with slope
- Rocker Bogie Mechanism can climb on steps having less height but there is a difficulty to climb on large height steps.
- Centre of Gravity position in each of the two operating modes, contrasting the response of these two distinctive configurations of the rocker-bogie suspension against upcoming obstacles that can be present along the system generated obstacles and roadblocks.

Using wifi module we can able to surveillance robot can able to detect object

A rover robot that can climb uneven surfaces and perform surveillance tasks would be a highly versatile and capable

machine. Such a robot would be ideal for various applications, including search and rescue missions, exploration in rough terrains, and security surveillance in challenging environments. Let's discuss the features, benefits associated with a rover robot designed for these purposes.

1. Mobility: The ability to climb uneven surfaces is crucial for navigating rough terrains. A rover robot with robust wheels, flexible legs, or a combination of both can negotiate obstacles such as rocks, stairs, and steep inclines. This mobility enables the robot to access areas that are inaccessible to wheeled robots or humans.

2. Autonomy: To operate efficiently, the rover robot should possess a level of autonomy. It should be able to navigate autonomously, plan routes, and make decisions based on the data received from its sensors. This autonomy allows the robot to perform surveillance tasks effectively without constant human intervention.

3. Communication: The robot should have a communication system that allows it to transmit data, images, and video feed to a control center or operators in real-time. This enables remote monitoring and surveillance, allowing operators to make informed decisions based on the information gathered by the robot.

4. Versatility: The ability to adapt to different environments and tasks is essential for a rover robot. It should be designed to accommodate additional modules or tools, such as manipulator arms, chemical sensors, or sample collection devices. This versatility ensures that the robot can be customized for specific surveillance or exploration missions.

VI. CONCLUSION

This project climbs the obstacles or ride on the abnormal surface with the help of such a rocker-bogie mechanism serves our objective because of its nature of allowing flexibility in linkages when wheel climb or goes from the abnormal road surface. Hence this mechanism does not need an extra suspension arrangement. The robot is controlled by using an application through the Wi-Fi module. Ultrasonic sensor also worked fine when obstacle found in front of the robot

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